

happy birthday
de stijl

Gerrit Rietveld, Schröder House

By Andreas 2309 - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0 <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=16886036>

chaotic?

>> the way it works

enlightenment!

lamp in Schröder House

the genesis may be ...

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semidetached house:

x - extension along the backwall

y - extension forward

z - extension upward